

CalcPlotAnomaly Matlab function set for the calculation and plotting of anomalies

USER MANUAL

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Functions for the calculation of anomalies of complete time series, specifying the month and the season.

CalcTSAomaly(TimeSerie)
CalcTSMonAnomaly(TimeSerie, Time, Month)
CalcTSSeasAnomaly(TimeSerie, Time, Season)

Functions for the calculation of anomalies of complete 3D grids, specifying the month and the season.

calcMatrixAnomaly(Grid)
calcMatrixMonAnomaly(Grid, Time, Month)
calcMatrixSeasAnomaly(Grid, Time, Season)

The grids can be 3D, depending on Lon, Lat, and Time or 4D, depending on Lon, Lat, Depth, and Time. In the case of 4D grids, the depth must be preset, reducing it to a 3D grid.

Functions for plotting anomalies

plotTSAnom
plotPointsTSAnom
plotAreaTSAnom
plotStairsTSAnom
plotBinaryTSAnom
plotBinaryBarTSAnom

Functions for plotting anomalies at a location

plotTSAnomAtLocation
plotPointsTSAnomAtLocation
plotAreaTSAnomAtLocation
plotStairsTSAnomAtLocation
plotBinaryTSAnomAtLocation
plotBinaryBarTSAnomAtLocation

Usage examples

```
lons = [-38.5, -38, -37.5, -37, -36.5, -36, -35.5];  
nLONS = length(lons);  
lats = [-1.5, -1, -0.5, 0, 0.5];  
nLATS = length(lats);  
depths = [1, 5, 10, 20, 30, 100];  
nDEPTHs = length(depths);  
timeRange = [datenum('2001-07-15'):30:datenum('2009-07-15')] - datenum('1900-01-01');  
nTIMES = length(timeRange);
```

```

TEMPERATURE = zeros(nLONS, nLATS, nDEPTHs, nTIMES);
for iDepth=1:nDEPTHs
    TTEMP(iTimes) = 25.0 + iTimes/2.0 * rand(1);
    for iTimes=1:nTIMES
        TEMPERATURE(:, :, iDepth, iTimes) = 25.0 + iTimes/2.0 * rand(7, 5) - depths(iDepth) * 0.2;
    end
end
end

```

```

createtime NC('testTSAnomaly.nc', timeRange, 'days since 1900-01-01')
inserttime NC('testTSAnomaly.nc', TTEMP, 'ts_TEMP', 'tsTemp', 'Fake temperature (Time
serie)', 'Â°C')
TSAnomaly = CalcTSAnomaly(TTEMP);
inserttime NC('testTSAnomaly.nc', TSAnomaly, 'ts_TEMP_anom', 'tsTemp', 'Fake
temperature (Anomaly)', 'Â°C')
figAnom = plotTSAnom(timeRange, TSAnomaly, 'Fake-temperature anomaly (\circC)');
print(figAnom, '-djpeg', '-r500', 'figAnomTS_Simple.jpeg');

```



```

figAnom = plotPointsTSAnom(timeRange, TSAnomaly, 'Fake-temperature anomaly (\circC)');
print(figAnom, '-djpeg', '-r500', 'figAnomTS_Points.jpeg');

```



```
figAnom = plotAreaTSAnom(timeRange, TSAnomaly, 'Fake-temperature anomaly (\circC)');
print(figAnom, '-djpeg', '-r500', 'figAnomTS_Area.jpeg');
```



```
figAnom = plotStairsTSAnom(timeRange, TSAnomaly, 'Fake-temperature anomaly (\circC)');
print(figAnom, '-djpeg', '-r500', 'figAnomTS_Stairs.jpeg');
```



```
figAnom = plotBinaryTSAnom(timeRange, TSAnomaly, 'Fake-temperature anomaly (\circC)');
print(figAnom, '-djpeg', '-r500', 'figAnomTS_Binary.jpeg');
```



```
figAnom = plotBinaryBarTSAnom(timeRange, TSAnomaly, 'Fake-temperature anomaly (\circC)');
print(figAnom, '-djpeg', '-r500', 'figAnomTS_BinaryBar.jpeg');
```



```
[TSAnomaly, newTimesRange] = CalcTSMonAnomaly(TSTEMP, timeRange, 7);
figAnom = plotBinaryTSAnom(newTimesRange, TSAnomaly, 'Fake-temperature anomaly (\circC)');
```

```
[TSAnomaly, newTimesRange] = CalcTSSeasAnomaly(TSTEMP, timeRange, 'SON');
figAnom = plotBinaryBarTSAnom(newTimesRange, TSAnomaly, 'Fake-temperature anomaly (\circC)');
```

```
TEMPERATURE(:,4,,:) = NaN;
TEMPERATURE(6, :, :) = NaN;
TEMPERATURE(2,3, :, 17) = NaN;
[LATS, LONS] = meshgrid(lats, lons);
create_NC_2DCoordinates('Matrix_Anomaly.nc', LONS, LATS);

inserttime_NC('Matrix_Anomaly.nc', timeRange, 'days since 1900-01-01');
```

```
insertdynamicvariable4D_NC('Matrix_Anomaly.nc', TEMPERATURE, 'temp', 'temperature',
'temperature at 3 m depth', 'Â°C', NaN);
MTXAnomaly = calcMatrixAnomaly(TEMPERATURE(:,:,3,:));
insertdynamicvariable3D_NC('Matrix_Anomaly.nc', MTXAnomaly, 'temp_anom', 'temperature
anomaly', 'temperature anomaly at 3m depth', 'Â°C', NaN);
```

```
figAnom = plotPointsTSAnomAtLocation([-37, -1], timeRange, MTXAnomaly, lons, lats, 'Fake-
temperature anomaly (\circC)');
print(figAnom, '-djpeg', '-r500', 'figAnom3mAtLocation_Points.jpeg');
```

```
figAnom = plotTSAnomAtLocation([-38, -1], timeRange, MTXAnomaly, lons, lats, 'Fake-
temperature anomaly (\circC)');
print(figAnom, '-djpeg', '-r500', 'figAnom3mAtLocation_Simple.jpeg');
```

```
figAnom = plotAreaTSAnomAtLocation([-38.5, -1], timeRange, MTXAnomaly, lons, lats, 'Fake-
temperature anomaly (\circC)');
print(figAnom, '-djpeg', '-r500', 'figAnom3mAtLocation_Area.jpeg');
```

```
figAnom = plotStairsTSAnomAtLocation([-38, 0], timeRange, MTXAnomaly, lons, lats, 'Fake-
temperature anomaly (\circC)');
print(figAnom, '-djpeg', '-r500', 'figAnom3mAtLocation_Stairs.jpeg');
```

```
figAnom = plotBinaryTSAnomAtLocation([-38.5, 0.5], timeRange, MTXAnomaly, lons, lats, 'Fake-
temperature anomaly (\circC)');
print(figAnom, '-djpeg', '-r500', 'figAnom3mAtLocation_Binary.jpeg');
```

```
figAnom = plotBinaryBarTSAnomAtLocation([-37.5, 0.5], timeRange, MTXAnomaly, lons, lats,
'Fake-temperature anomaly (\circC)');
print(figAnom, '-djpeg', '-r500', 'figAnom3mAtLocation_BinaryBar.jpeg');
```

```
[MTXAnomaly, newTimesRange] = calcMatrixMonAnomaly(TEMPERATURE(:,:,1,:), timeRange,
3);
[MTXAnomaly, newTimesRange] = calcMatrixSeasAnomaly(TEMPERATURE(:,:,6,:), timeRange,
'JJA');
figAnom = plotTSAnomAtLocation([-37, -1], newTimesRange, MTXAnomaly, lons, lats, 'Fake-
temperature anomaly (\circC)');
figAnom = plotBinaryTSAnomAtLocation([-38.5, 0.5], newTimesRange, MTXAnomaly, lons, lats,
'Fake-temperature anomaly (\circC)');
figAnom = plotBinaryBarTSAnomAtLocation([-37, -1], newTimesRange, MTXAnomaly, lons, lats,
'Fake-temperature anomaly (\circC)');
```

Download functions

All functions for handling NetCDF files can be downloaded from:

<https://zenodo.org/record/5572749>

Cite these functions as:

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